

Prevalence, Knowledge, and Risk Factors Related to Shisha Smoking Among Students at the Technical Institute of Mosul

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Abstract

Background: Hookah Smoking is very popular among men and women (young men, old men, and women). In spite of this, it is a severe risk to health and represents one of the major causes of worldwide death, and the scientific studies have supported that smoking through hookah as an alternative to smoking tobacco has many dangerous effects on human health.

Methods: A sample of 210 participants was selected randomly by choosing the odd number from the Mosul Technical Institute students for the period from 1 October 2020 to 1 January 2021. A questionnaire was used to interview the students who took part in the present study in order to estimate the prevalence of shisha smoking among the participating sample; the respondents were given a brief idea of the study objectives, and their knowledge of shisha smoking and related diseases was verified through a questionnaire. Data were analyzed using frequency and percentage. The study has been approved by the ethics committee of the institute.

Results: The result showed that out of 210 students who participated in this study, there were 58 smokers, 22 (34%) of them smoked shisha alone, 15 (23%) smoked cigarettes only, and 28 (43%) smoked hookah and cigarettes. The highest percentage of hookah smokers (71.0%) was in the age group (21-23), compared to 0.5% in the age group (27+). Most students avoided smoking in front of the family (78.6%) while they preferred to smoke a hookah with friends (66.2%). The majority of the participating answered that hookah smoking is more expensive than cigarettes (67.1%), and that is the reason for their preference for cigarettes over hookah, with a mean of 0.48, SD of 0.50, and 51.9%. Regarding the degree of students' awareness in general about whether smoking shisha is less dangerous to health than smoking cigarettes, the degree of knowledge was weak. It was found that the cognitive level was poor and acceptable among the majority of the sample (67%). Regarding the prevalence of behavioral beliefs associated with hookah smoking, the survey indicated that the prevalence of correct ideas and beliefs prevailing among the sample members reached 53% and that 47% of the sample members had a wrong idea about the prevalence of hookah. Also, the association between the duration of smoking and study specialization was shown to be statistically significant ($p=0.75^*$).

Conclusion: Hookah smoking is still a popular health-threatening behavior for college students and young adults. This study indicated that there is a

More Information

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high percentage of hookah smoking among the study sample and that the participants in this study lack sufficient knowledge, lack of awareness, and the beliefs and misconceptions associated with hookah smoking, which requires governmental measures to reduce the harmful spread among students.

Introduction

All over the world, hookah smoking is considered a threat to public health. It has been widely used throughout the Middle East and North Africa for centuries, having begun in India and Pakistan in the 17th century. However, during the last 20 years, it has extended to other areas of the globe, just like it did in Europe and North America, and its consumption among teenagers and young adults in the above countries has also increased dramatically [1]. There are a number of other names for the hookah, such as shisha, argileh, waterpipe, and narghile. An example of a tobacco pipe is the smokehouse, which is a long, flexible tube that leads smoke into a bowl [2]. In most Western as well as developing countries, hookah smoking has become very popular, especially among young people [3].

Because of beliefs and misconceptions, many practitioners of the hookah smoking habit believe that its smoke has less negative impact on health than cigarettes, as they believe that inhaling smoke that contains fruit flavors (such as grapes, bananas, apples, etc.) is less harmful and toxic through filtration effects provided by water hookahs [4,5]. These toxic substances are found in nicotine, carbon monoxide, nearby polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, nitric oxides, formaldehyde, and others [6-8], so, the amount of smoke generated by a hookah may be up to 48.6 times more than that of a single cigarette, even if the user only smokes for less than an hour during a single session [9,10].

Because of the misconceptions and misunderstandings of many, hookah smoking is less detrimental than cigarette smoking. Multiple scientific investigations have shown that hookah smoke includes carcinogenic compounds [6,8]. Also, a single cigarette may contain far higher levels of toxic substances than a puff of hookah smoke [9]. Hookah smoking has become an unknown and non-traditional type of tobacco use among university students and is associated with many health problems, including addiction, various types of cancer, and lung diseases [11]. Besides cancer, it induces many respiratory illnesses, since nicotine in cigarette smoke attenuates the immune response that safeguards the body against cancerous growth [4].

In fact, tobacco smoke contains several carcinogenic chemicals, which are the principal cause of various cancer types in the body, especially lung cancer [12]. Tobacco smoking ranks as the second main cause of mortality globally, accounting for one in ten adult deaths worldwide [13]. It was recently estimated that 100 million individuals globally engage in daily hookah

smoking [14]. Smoking hookah became more prevalent in Mosul after the liberation, where smoking was forbidden [15].

Materials and Methods

Subjects and Methods

A descriptive analysis A cross-sectional survey study was done to evaluate the prevalence, level of knowledge, and risk factors related to hookah smoking among a participants of Mosul Technical Institute students for the period from 1 October 2020 to 1 January 2021. The sample consisted of 210 participants between the ages of 18 and 27 from various departments (administrative, agricultural, technological, and medical).

A questionnaire was used to interview the students participating in present study in order to evaluate the prevalence of shisha smoking; the respondents were given a brief idea of the study objectives, and their knowledge of shisha smoking and related diseases was verified through a questionnaire.

The questionnaire consists of personal information like age, social status, educational level, residence, academic major, and prevalence. Tobacco use and behavioral beliefs associated with hookah smoking. such as, do you smoke hookah more when you are with family or friends? Is hookah smoking more expensive than cigarettes? Do you smoke hookah only on occasions? Is smoking shisha a manifestation of masculinity? Is the reason for smoking shisha to relieve stress in life and get rid of boredom and psychological problems? Do you think hookah is considered a civilized social condition?

As for the questions about the risk factors related to hookah smoking, they are as follows: Do you believe that smoking shisha has a lower health risk than smoking cigarettes? Is smoking shisha at home not harmful to the health of the family?

Do you think that when smoking hookah, the water in the pipe filters away the hazardous compounds in the smoke? Do you think that one of the diseases caused by smoking hookah is lung cancer? Do you think that smoking hookah causes skin diseases and eczema? Do you believe that smoking hookah may lead to lip cancer? Do you believe that cardiovascular illness is one of the ailments associated with smoking shisha? Do you believe that respiratory infections are among the ailments attributable to hookah smoking? Do you think that smoking hookah harms the immune system? Do you think that smoking shisha pollutes the environment less than cigarettes?

Statistical Analysis

It performed by entering and coding data using Microsoft Excel 2021 for each questionnaire and using the SPSS version statistical program (28). The statistical approach to the data consists of a descriptive approach that includes a scale "frequencies, percentage, mean scores, standard deviation, and chi-square, and a p-value less than 0.05 indicates statistical significance."

Score Calculation

Regarding the knowledge, a scoring of knowledge agreed upon by assigning a score of (3) for the right answer and (2) for the incomplete (I don't know) answer and a score of (1) for the wrong answer. Number of questions: 12 Minimum=12 Maximum=36 Medium=24 The median was computed for each question, with scores below the median being bad and scores equal to or above 24 classified as acceptable or excellent.

Results

Socio-Demographic Characteristics

Of the 210 students who participated in this study, 58 are smokers, only 22 (34%) smoke hookah, and only 15 (23%) smoke cigarettes alone, and 28 (43%) smoke hookah and cigarettes. The participants' ages vary from 18 to over 27, with a mean age (21.993± 1.540) for the water pipe smokers with a p-value of < 0.001. The highest percentage of waterpipe smokers were (71.0%) in the age group (21-23) compared to (0.5. %) in the age group (27+). The majority of smokers were single (89%); results showed that the proportion of smoking in urban areas is higher (75.2%). According to the education level of study, we showed that the majority of smokers of shisha were among the administration departments (43.3%) compared with technology and medical and health (17.6%) (18.1%), respectively. Table 1. 2. 3. 4.

Table 1: Distribution of the Study Sample Based on the Age Group

Age (years)	F.	%
18 - 20	40	19.0
21 – 23	149	71.0
24 – 26	20	9.5
27 +	1	0.5
Total	210	100.0
Mean	21.99	
SD.	1.540	
P-value	< 0.001	

Table 2: Distribution of the Study Sample Based on Marital Status

Marital Status	F.	%
Single	187	89.0
Marred	23	11.0
Total	210	100.0

Table 3: Distribution of Study Sample Based on Residence

Marital Status	F.	%
Urban	158	75.2
Rural	52	24.7
Total	210	100.0

Table4: The Distribution of Study Sample According to Level of Education

Study specialization	F.	%
Medical	38	18.1
Administration	91	43.3
Agricultural	44	21.0
Technology	37	17.6
Total	210	100.0

Tobacco Use Prevalence and Behavioral Beliefs Related to Water Pipe Smoking and the Method of Shisha Smoking, Reasons & the Motivation

Interviewer answers show the prevalence of shisha smoking and the factors influencing its increase. The mean of hookah smoking with the family was (0.21) with an SD (0.411), while the mean of hookah smoking with friends was (0.66) and SD (0.47), as most students avoided smoking in front of the family (78.6%) while they preferred to smoke a hookah with friends (66.2%). Regarding the average cost of hookah smoking relative to cigarettes with an average (0.67) SD (0.47), the majority of the sample answered that hookah smoking is more expensive than cigarettes (67.1%), and that is the reason for their preference for cigarettes over hookah with a mean (0.48) SD (0.50) and (51.9%). A total of 210 participants were enrolled in the study, with a mean (0.57) and an SD (0.497) of students who smoke shisha because they believe that it relieves psychological and family pressure and relieves them of boredom. While the majority of the sample showed that hookah smoking is not considered a developed civilization phenomenon and is not considered a manifestation of masculinity from their point of view (72.9%) (86.2%), respectively (Table 5).

Table 5: Distribution of the Studied Sample According to Personal Information Behavioral Beliefs Associated with Water pipe Smoking and the Method of Shisha Smoking, Reasons & Motivation

List	Items	Answer	F.	%	Mean	SD.
1	Do you smoke more shisha when you are with the family?	Yes	45	21.4	0.21	0.411
		No	165	78.6		

2	Do you smoke more shisha when you are with friends?	Yes	139	66.2	0.66	0.474
		No	71	33.8		
3	Do you prefer smoking hookah to cigarettes?	Yes	101	48.1	0.48	0.501
		No	109	51.9		
4	smoking hookah more expensive than cigarettes?	Yes	141	67.1	0.67	0.471
		No	69	32.9		
		No	78	37.1		
5	Is the reason for smoking hookah that it relieves the pressure of life and gets rid of boredom and family and psychological problems?	Yes	119	56.7	0.57	0.497
		No	91	43.3		
6	In your opinion, is hookah considered a civilized social condition?	Yes	57	27.1	0.27	0.45
		No	153	72.9		
7	Do you see shisha smoking as a manifestation of masculinity?	Yes	29	13.8	0.14	0.35
		No	181	86.2		

And the association between the duration of smoking and study specialization was shown to be statistically

significant ($p=0.75^*$), and the mean was (2.23) for the duration of smoking between (4-6) years.

Table 6: The Association Between the Duration of Smoking and Study Specialization

Duration of smoking	Medical		Administration		Agricultural		Technology		Total		Mean	SD.	P-value
	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%			
1-3	48	47.06	16	15.69	22	21.57	16	15.69	102	100	2.06	1.15	0.75
4-6	35	38.89	17	18.89	20	22.22	18	20.00	90	100	2.23	1.171	
7+	8	44.44	5	27.78	2	11.11	3	16.67	18	100	2	1.138	

Regarding students' knowledge about whether hookah smoking is less dangerous to health than cigarette smoking, only (22.9%) of the students answered correctly. Regarding the overall students' knowledge score was poor.

As for the answer to the question (Does smoking shisha at home cause health damage to the family?), only (74.3%) were answered correctly.

In fact, the water in a hookah does not filter out the toxic substances in the smoke; only (21.9%) of the students answered correctly. While (28.1) did not know the answer and (50.0) gave a wrong answer.

Students' answers to questions related to their knowledge of one of the diseases caused by smoking hookah are lung cancer; the majority of students (72.4%) answered correctly, while (14.3%) did not know the answer and (13.3%) answered. It is wrong that hookah smoking does not cause lung cancer.

According to the students' answers about the relationship of hookah smoking with skin diseases and lip cancer (41.4%, 59.5%), they answered correctly

(35.7%, 21.4%); their answer was wrong and (22.9%, 19.0%) did not know the answer.

About the students' answers about the relationship of hookah smoking with cardiovascular diseases and respiratory infections (75.7%, 73.8%), they answered correctly (13.3%, 9%) their answer was wrong (11.0%, 17.1%) did not know the answer.

With regard to the students' answer about the relationship of hookah smoking to the immune system and the transmission of diseases among smokers (46.2%,51.9%) respectively, they answered correctly (36.7%, 22.4%) their answer was wrong (17.1%, 25.7%) did not know the answer.

Regarding the students' answer about whether hookah smoking pollutes the environment to a lesser degree than cigarettes and whether hookah smoking causes an increase in the mortality rate, the majority of the students answered incorrectly and did not know the answer, while the correct answer represented (34.8%, 46.7%) respectively. Table7.

Table 7: Knowledge Score About the Health Risks of Hookah Smoking

List	Items	Answer	N.	%	Mean	SD.	Ass.
1	Do you think that smoking hookah is less dangerous to health than smoking cigarettes?	Yes	129	61.4	1.39	0.835	Poor
		No	48	22.9			
		I don't no	33	15.7			
2		Yes	156	74.3	1.61	0.712	Good

	Does smoking shisha at home not cause health damage to the family?	No	28	13.3			
		I don't no	26	12.4			
3	Do you think that when smoking hookah, the toxic substances in the smoke are filtered out by the water in the pipe?	Yes	105	50.0	1.28	0.802	Poor
		No	46	21.9			
		I don't no	59	28.1			
4	Do you think that one of the diseases caused by smoking hookah is lung cancer?	Yes	152	72.4	1.59	0.715	Good
		No	28	13.3			
		I don't no	30	14.3			
5	Do you think that smoking hookah causes skin diseases and eczema?	Yes	87	41.4	1.06	0.879	Poor
		No	75	35.7			
		I don't no	48	22.9			
6	Do you think that one of the diseases caused by smoking hookah is lip cancer?	Yes	125	59.5	1.38	0.817	Poor
		No	45	21.4			
		I don't no	40	19.0			
7	Do you think that one of the diseases caused by smoking shisha is cardiovascular disease?	Yes	159	75.7	1.62	0.710	Good
		No	28	13.3			
		I don't no	23	11.0			
8	Do you think that respiratory infections are one of the diseases caused by smoking hookah?	Yes	155	73.8	1.65	0.641	Good
		No	19	9.0			
		I don't no	36	17.1			
9	Do you think that smoking hookah harms the immune system?	Yes	97	46.2	1.10	0.907	Poor
		No	77	36.7			
		I don't no	36	17.1			
10	Do you think that smoking hookah transmits diseases among smokers?	Yes	109	51.9	1.30	0.812	Poor
		No	47	22.4			
		I don't no	54	25.7			
11	Do you think that smoking shisha pollutes the environment less than cigarettes?	Yes	73	34.8	0.89	0.893	Poor
		No	96	45.7			
		I don't no	41	19.5			
12	Does smoking hookah increase death rates?	Yes	98	46.7	1.20	0.831	Poor
		No	55	26.2			
		I don't no	57	27.1			

As for calculating the score of students' knowledge about the most dangerous to health (hookah or cigarettes?), the correct answer was (6 1.4%), and the cognitive degree was weak, while the wrong answers represented (22.9%), where the cognitive degree was. It was good. And (15.7) of the sample answered that they did not know the answer and that the result was classified as bad.

As for the answer to the question (smoking hookah at home causes health damage to the family), the majority of students answered correctly (74.3%), while a small group of them answered incorrectly (13.3%) and (12.4%) did not know the answer to the question. The knowledge score was good.

In fact, when smoking a hookah, the toxic substances in the smoke are not filtered by the water in the pipe; only (21.9%) of the students answered correctly. While (28.1) did not know the answer and (50.0) gave a wrong answer. The knowledge score was poor.

Regarding the students' question about whether lung cancer is a disease caused by smoking hookah, their cognitive scores were good, as the majority of students (72.4%) answered correctly, while (14.3%) did not know the answer and (13.3%) answered incorrectly that hookah smoking does not cause lung cancer.

According to the students' answers about the relationship of hookah smoking with skin diseases and lip cancer (41.4%, 59.5%), they answered correctly (35.7%, 21.4%) and their answer was wrong (22.9%, 19.0%). The answer was not known, so the result was assessed as poor.

About the students' answers about the relationship of hookah smoking with cardiovascular diseases and respiratory infections (75.7%, 73.8%), they answered correctly; their cognitive scores were good (13.3%, 9%); their answer was wrong; and (11.0%, 17.1%) did not know the answer.

With regard to the students' answer about the relationship of hookah smoking to the immune system

and the transmission of diseases among smokers (46.2%, 51.9%), they answered correctly (36.7%, 22.4%) their answer was wrong (17.1%, 25.7%); and they did not know the answer. The result was assessed as poor. Regarding the students' answer about whether hookah smoking pollutes the environment to a lesser degree than cigarettes and whether hookah smoking causes an increase in the mortality rate, the majority of the students answered incorrectly and did not know the answer, while the correct answer represented (34.8%, 46.7%). The result was assessed as poor. (Table 6). The overall knowledge level was found good among 4 (33%) of students & 8 (67%) of students' knowledge scores were observed as acceptable & poor.

With regard to the overall prevalence of behavioral beliefs associated with hookah smoking, The study showed that the prevalence of correct ideas and beliefs prevailing among the sample is 112 (53%) and that 98 (47%) of the sample have a wrong idea about the prevalence of shisha. Figure1.

Figure 1: Overall Prevalence of Shisha Smoking

The overall knowledge level was found to be good among 4 (33%) of students, & 8 (67%) of students' knowledge scores were observed as acceptable & poor.

Figure 2: Total Scores of the Knowledge

Discussion

One of the most important reasons for fear of the deterioration of the general health situation in society is the attraction of young people to smoking shisha, including university students, because its addiction among young people may lead to serious health

complications, as many studies have shown that smoking shisha has become more common among young people who represent the active part and support basic production in the country.

Distribution of the studied sample according to age group and marital status. In this study, the highest percentage of hookah smokers (71.0%) was in the age group (21-23) this study contradicts the study by Maziak [16], which found the average age of starting hookah smoking (19.2) years, and with the study in AL-Nasiriya Technical Institute Student by Salam Hussein Owaida et al. [17], and study by Al-Mousawi [18] where it was found, the average age of initiation of hookah smoking is (17.4) years. The 21–23 age group had the greatest frequency of CS and WPS.

Across all age groups at the age of 24; they have a lot of social and academic pressures, which may explain why they smoke more to alleviate their dissatisfaction and anxiety. The high percentage might also be related to the cheap prices. According to the current study, about 89% of smokers among students are unmarried, and these results do not agree with another study by Al-Mousawi [18], where it was found that hookah smoking among unmarried Karbala University students was 45.7%.

According to the education level of study, we showed that the majority of smokers of shisha were among the administration departments 43.3 % compared with technology and medical and health (17.6%) (18.1%) respectively; this may be due to the fact that the administrative departments are not fully aware of the dangers of smoking hookah.

In our study, friends played a large role in encouraging hookah smoking. As most of the students preferred to smoke shisha with friends (66.2%), while most of the students avoided smoking in front of their parents (78.6%), which is Studies by Smith-Simon et al. [19], and Ward et al. [20] revealed that most hookah smokers smoke more with friends. This explains the effect of friend pressure on hookah smoking, and different studies, such as Muhammad et al. [21] in Kuwait and Maziak et al. [16], showed the effect of friends on hookah smoking.

Some smokers believe that smoking puts them in a position of coping and rapprochement with their mates; this may be due to the feeling of family and social instability, which makes them practice the habit of smoking shisha in order to get rid of this feeling, as when they gather, everyone smokes. Gaining friends acceptance and feeling of personality can without much of a stretch, be obtained by smoking [22]. In terms of perceived health risks, (61.4) in this study, hookah smoking is believed to be less hazardous to health than cigarette smoking. This result is consistent with some previous studies by Shafagoj et al. [23], and Ward et al. [20], and a study by Labib et al. [24], which

showed that 74% of students stated that hookah is less harmful, and Maziak et al. [16], where it was shown that 89% of students believe that cigarettes are more harmful than shisha. Al-Moussawi's study found that (90.9%) believe that smoking hookah is harmful to health [18].

In this study only (22.9), they knew that hookah smoking is more dangerous to health than cigarette smoking, and this is consistent with Al-Moussawi's study, which found that (90.9%) believe that hookah smoking is harmful to health. Maziak et al. [16] reported the opposite when they found that 89% of students believed cigarettes to be more harmful than water pipes. It is often believed that hookah smoking has no health risks because the smoke passes through the water and is filtered. Kandela, [25] but the scientific fact is that when smoking hookah, that the toxic substances in the smoke are not filtered by the water in the pipe, where only (21.9%) of the students answered correctly. This finding agreed with some of the previous studies by Shafagoj et al. [23] and Ward et al. [20]. It is wrong that hookah smoking does not cause cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. In the current study the majority of the students answered correctly; this finding was consistent with results conducted in Turkey and Saudi Arabia [26]. Compared to cigarette and bidi smoking, hookah smoking is far more harmful to the lungs and may lead to chronic bronchitis.

According to the students' answers about the relationship of hookah smoking with gum and lip cancer (41.4%, 59.5%), they answered correctly (35.7%, 21.4%); their answer was wrong (22.9%, 19.0%) and they did not know the answer. A study in Saudi Arabia demonstrated an association between periodontal disease, evaluated by probing depth, and both waterpipe and cigarette use [27].

With regard to the overall prevalence of behavioral beliefs associated with hookah smoking. The study demonstrated that the prevalence of correct ideas and beliefs prevailing among the sample is 53% and that 47% of the sample have a wrong idea about the prevalence of shish. This results similar to the study by Mousawi [18], indicated that the prevalence of narghile smoking among the University of Karbala students was 45.7%, and study directed by Dar-Odeh in a Jordanian, [28] they found that 44.1% of students were smoking narghile. Likewise, in a study of Al-Turki et al. [29], it was showed that 42.1% of the students in central Saudi Arabia were smoking narghile and that 24.6% were smoking both narghile and cigarettes.

Conclusion

Hookah smoking is still a popular health-threatening behavior for college students and young adults. This study revealed that university students use hookahs at a high frequency and that the participants in this study lack sufficient knowledge, lack awareness, and have the

beliefs and misconceptions associated with hookah smoking, which requires governmental measures to reduce the negative spread of hookah use among students.

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